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ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF LAND USE/LAND COVER CHANGES ON GULLY ERODED LANDSCAPE IN GOMBE METROPOLIS, GOMBE STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Gully erosion is a critical global issue that hinders sustainable development in agriculture and general land use. Therefore, this study analyses the impact of land use/land cover changes on gully eroded landscape in Gombe Metropolis, Gombe State, Nigeria with the following objectives: analysis of the landuse/Landcover changes in Gombe Metropolis, examine the gully eroded landscape expansion in the Study area from 1993 to 2023 and analyses causal relationship between Land use /Land cover Change and Gully Eroded Landscapes Expansion. The study used low resolution landsat imageries covering the study area were used for analysis in GIS environment to extract landuse-Landcover parameters and the extent of gully eroded land in the study area. The study employed correlation and regression statistical tools to analyze the relationship and impact of landuse/cover changes on gully eroded land extent. The study revealed that the built-up area experienced a steady increase from 10.85km² in 1993 to 49.94 km² in 2023, while vegetated areas decreased from 8.8km² in 1993 to only 1.98km² in 2023. The total area covered by gully eroded land in the study area is 44.95 sq km. However, there is a surprising negative relationship between urban vegetation and rainfall. Vegetation cover is a major driver of erosion, and there is a weak positive relationship between built-up and vegetation, and built-up and eroded land area. More so, landuse/landcover variables were observed to have statistically significant impact or causal relationship with gully eroded landscape in Gombe metropolis ($p = 0.002$, $R^2 = 0.564$, $df = 6$, $F = 5.453$, $SE = 2.34556E$). this study concluded that gully erosion development in the study area is on the increase as influenced by changes in the rate of land use land cover, which is causing serious land degradation thereby affecting the people and their economic activities. The study calls for protective strategies and measures for environmental management to reduce gully erosion development and better land use conservation practices. Changes in land use planning in Gombe metropolis should be made to address expansion and drought-resistant plants like *Pitadeniastrum africanum* (kashe kwari or kafi kansila) can effectively help in gully erosion control.*

Keywords: Land Use, Land Cover, Gully Erosion, Landscape, Geographic information system.

INTRODUCTION

Gully erosion is simply a systematic removal of top soil, including plant nutrients, from the land surface by various agents of denudation. It occurs in several parts of Nigeria under different geological, climatic and soil conditions. Gully erosion creates channels that

are fluvial with geometric attributes of depth and width, but the degree of occurrence varies considerably from one part of the country to the other (Amanawa, 2024).

Gully Erosion is a natural phenomenon; however, when accelerated, it causes social, environment and economic losses, affecting

not only the area itself, but there are also off-site impacts (Amanawa, 2024). Over the past several decades, gullies have become a very important issue worldwide. The acceleration in the number of gullies is connected with human interference beginning in the 18th century, which has modified and intensified natural rates of soil removal and deposits (Amanawa, 2024). In India, this problem is related to improper management of runoff, deforestation, overgrazing and incorrect agricultural activities. Lack of rural conservative practices and the excess of mechanization are the causes in Latin America. In Europe, USA, China and Africa, many studies have shown a high level of soil loss in gullies over the years (Sampaio, 2022).

Land use/land cover (LULC) is a framework that categorizes the physical characteristics of land and how it is utilized by humans. Land cover refers to the natural and artificial elements covering the earth's surface, such as forests, water bodies, and urban areas. In contrast, land use focuses on the activities or purposes for which the land is used, such as agriculture, residential, or commercial activities. This distinction helps in understanding environmental management and urban planning. LULC change is the prompt influence and response of human activities upon nature followed by significant consequences. Anthropogenic factors play a vital role in land-use changes of any area and LULC is commonly based on urban growth. Scientific analysis in these areas is highly essential to better understand the growth patterns and processes. Accurate, consistent, and updated information on the urbanization trend is crucial for the need analysis and policy formulation to ensure a sustainable urban future (Rimal, 2018). Thus, the monitoring of spatio-temporal expansion of the cities and accurate prediction of LULC

change is vital for ecosystem conservation and sustainable development management strategies to be implemented globally (Mehra, 2024).

LULC changes are evident in Nigerian cities as with other developing nations of the world. Being one of the most urbanized countries in the African continent with an estimated urbanization rate of 3.5% annually, Nigeria has witnessed tremendous urban expansion over the years (Aruya, 2019). Geo information and remote sensing technologies present the most suitable tools for monitoring and planning land use, as well as examining LULC change from a local to a global scale (Aruya, 2019).

Gully erosion is the detachment and transport of soil particles by erosive agents, most commonly water and/or wind. Soils generally take thousands of years to develop from their original parent material, and natural erosion is a part of this development process. Vegetation protects soil, and its roots hold and bind soil particles together, so that in long-term natural systems (e.g., forests and prairies) soil losses in upland areas may be relatively minimal (Anindya, 2022). Gully erosion is a significant environmental issue worldwide, with the problem worsening due to population growth, land use/land cover changes and climate change. Gombe metropolis in Nigeria, located in the semi-arid zone of Nigeria, is facing this major environmental disaster. Gully erosion is observed to have caused severe havocs on road, houses, culverts and threats to human and animal lives in the study area. Moreover, the infrastructural development and demographic increase have exacerbated the problem, with large areas becoming unsuitable for human settlements. Also, global warming is contributing to the risk of gully erosion, particularly in semi-arid zones.

It is important to note that the relationship between gully erosion and land use practices is complex and interconnected. Implementing sustainable land management practices that promote soil conservation and water retention can help mitigate the impacts of land use choices on gully eroded landscape. Hence, the need to analyse the impact of land use/land cover changes on gully eroded landscape in Gombe Metropolis, Gombe State, Nigeria.

STUDY AREA

Gombe Metropolis, lies between, latitudes 10°16'48"N and 10°17'24"N and longitudes 11°14'07"E and 11°4'42"E. It is bounded by Kwami LGA to the North, Akko LGA to the Southwest, and Yamaltu Deba LGA to the East, with a total land mass of 52km. Gombe metropolis has a projected population figure of 450,000 people estimated (3.3% annual change) (National Population Commission, 2022) (see Figure 2). The vegetation of the local government is typical of that of Gombe State which is Sudan Savannah and experience two distinct season, dry season

which normally commences from November-March and rainy season from April- October with mean annual rainfall of 863.2mm. Agriculture is the major occupation in the region (mostly Peasant farmers) while some engage in business and few are civil servants. Gombe state is located in the Sudan savannah region of Nigeria in the North-East of river Benue and East of Yankari Game Reserve bordering with Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno and Yobe states covering a total area of 18.768 km² with a population projection (2022) of about 3,960,100. The approximate altitude of Gombe ranges from 400-500m above mean sea level. The climate of Gombe local government is part of the extreme tropical continental types one of the basic characteristics of the climate zone is relatively short rainy season on a comparability long dry season, the beginning and the end of the rainy season fluctuate from year to year in the study area; it usually begins in late April to early May and end in September or October. The mean annual rainfall ranges between (161-210mm). The dry season in the area last for six to seven months from late October to late April or early may (Mbaya, 2022).

Figure 1: Study Area Map (Gombe Metropolis)
Source: Geographic Information System Lab, FUK, Gombe (2025)

Topography is mainly mountainous, undulating and hilly to the southeast and open plains in the central North East, West and Northwest (Bello, 2014). Gombe metropolis has a land cover of 28000 hectares with 15km radius (Gombe master plan, 2003:2030). Generally, the geology of the study area developed on complex geologic crystalline bedrocks most of which are insulated by incised crystalline basement complex of sedimentary formation, the late cretaceous period has greatly influenced the topography of the area which leads to the subsequent dissection and stream incision in the area (Mbaya, 202). The soils of the study area are ferruginous types. They consist of unconsolidated wind-blown or water deposited sand and clay-rich mostly to the

southeast of the metropolis along the valley of Pantami catchment (Amos *et al*, 2015).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ground-truthing of the study area was undertaken, in order to have adequate knowledge of the study area for better classification scheme and identifications of the gully sides. It also helped the researcher to get acquainted with the study area and also to collect coordinates for training site for the image classification.

TYPES AND SOURCE OF DATA USED

The types and sources of data used for this research is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: The types of Data Collected

Data Required	Data source
Landsat 9 Image covering Gombe between (1993, 2003, 2013, 2023) was used for extracting information on gully eroded land.	USGS.gov. Earth explorer website of the United States Geological Survey (USGS).
Data on the rate of change in the land cover between 1993-2023 imagery satellites.	Earth explorer website of the United States Geological Survey (USGS).

Source: Authors (2025)

DATA PROCESSING

Landsat data with 30m resolution were used for the study. The clipped images were subjected to digital image processing to enhance the image contrast and to remove obscurity for proper identification. This was necessary because some of the features captured in the satellite imagery were not sharp enough for identification. Hence, histogram equalization was used to improve the pictorial quality of the image.

Layer Stacking: During layer stacking, the Universal Traverse Mercator (UTM) system with WGS84 as a datum was assigned as a preference as far as projection was concerned. All bands of Landsat 5 TM, 7 ETM⁺ and 8 OLI excluding the thermal band were considered for Layers stacking. The nature of these different bands had to be considered to make a decision as to which three band combination would be most helpful for classification and visual interpretation. Table 2 shows that false colour composite which was employed in this study.

Table 2: Band Combination.

Landsat Type	Year	Band Combination	Composite Type
Landsat 5 TM	1993	Band 4, 3 & 2	False Colour Composite
Landsat 5 TM	1998	Band 4, 3 & 2	False Colour Composite
Landsat 7 ETM+	2003	Band 4, 3 & 2	False Colour Composite
Landsat 7 ETM+	2008	Band 4, 3 & 2	False Colour Composite
Landsat 8 OLI	2013	Band 5, 4 & 3	False Colour Composite
Landsat 8 OLI	2018	Band 5, 4 & 3	False Colour Composite
Landsat 8 OLI	2023	Band 5, 4 & 3	False Colour Composite

Source: Authors (2025)

DATA ANALYSIS

The types of data were analyzed based on objectives of the study as follows:

Analyze the rate of land use /land cover changes in the study area between 1993-2023: To achieved this, the supervised classification, the image analyst supervises the pixel categorization process by specifying to the computer algorithm; numerical descriptors of

the various land cover types present in the scene.

A supervised classification was performed on false color composites (bands 4, 3 and 2 for Landsat 5 and 7, and bands 5, 4 and 3 for Landsat 8) into the following land use and land cover classes; built-up area, bareland, vegetation cover, farmland and eroded land using the classification scheme adopted from Anderson *et al.*, (1976) (see Table 3).

Table 3: Classification Scheme.

Code	Landuse/Landcover	Description
1	Farmland land	Lands used for farming (plantation, cropland orchard)
2	Built-up land	Lands used for residential, industrial, commercial, etc.
3	Grassland/vegetation cover	Lands covered with natural vegetation (any plant species)
4	Bareland	Lands devoid of vegetation,
5	Eroded Land	Dry rivers/streams and exposed soil

Sources: Modified from Anderson *et al.*, (1976).

The Landsat TM, ETM and Landsat 8 was utilized to obtained different layers and the layer will be stacked together using ERDAS Imagine 9.2 software; subset of the study area will be obtained using the ERDAS imagine software subset tool. ERDAS imagine was used for the pixel-based classification. Supervised classification was carried out using maximum likelihood classifier since it is

a land-use/land cover classification which produced the output raster layer. Maximum likelihood algorithm was used to classify the images and the digital numbers of the pixels were grouped with pixels arranged and organized otherwise known as land cover classes built-up, vegetation, bare land, agricultural area, water bodies as suggested by

U.S.G.S classification system (Anderson’s Classification, 1971).

To estimate the annual rate of gully eroded land expansion in the study area from 1993-2023. The extent and rate of change of gullies eroded land in the study area between 1993-1998, 1998-2003, 2003-2008, 2008-2013, 2013-2018, and 2019-2023 was calculated by subtracting the area coverage of the base year from the reference year thus:

$$\text{Magnitude} = \text{Reference Year} - \text{Base year (e.g. 1993-1998)}$$

While the rate of changes for water body in the study area was determined following these steps:

Step 1

Percentage change was calculated by dividing magnitude change by the base year (the initial year) and multiplied by 100 thus:

$$\text{Percentage change} = \frac{\text{Magnitude of change}}{\text{Base Year}} \times 100$$

Step 2

The Annual rate of change is calculated by dividing the percentage change by the number of study period 1993 – 1998 (5years), 1998-2003 (19years) and 1993-2023 (30years) thus:

$$\text{Annual rate of change} = \frac{\text{Percentage Change}}{\text{Period}}$$

To examine the causal relationship between land use/land cover change and gully eroded land expansion. To achieve this state objective, data on the extent of each LULC and gully was used to conduct a Pearson correlation parametric statistical test. This method was used to examines the relationship between land use/land cover and gully eroded land expansion in the study area. Below is a formula for calculating the Pearson correlation coefficient (*r*): (equation. 6)

$$r = \frac{n \sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

where

The coefficient

(r) is a number between -1 and 1, (0) is no correlation, 1 is positive correlation, - 1 is negative correlation. (N) Number of Pears data x_i - values of the x-variable in a sample, \bar{x} - mean of the values of the x-variable, y_i - values of the y-variable in a sample. \bar{y} - mean of the values of the y-variable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RATE OF LAND USE/LAND COVER CHANGES IN THE STUDY AREA BETWEEN 1993 AND 2023

EXTENT OF LAND USE/LAND COVER

Table 4 shows the seven major LULC types classification and the area extent (built-up, eroded land, rock outcrop, vegetation, farmland, bare land, and water body) were classified for the years of 1993, 1998, 2003, 2008, 2013, 2018 and 2023.

Table 4: Classes and Extent of Land Use Land Cover

LULC		1993	1998	2003	2008	2013	2018	2023
Built-up	Ha	10.85	10.91	13.63	18.04	22.61	43.64	49.94
	%	10.5	10.5	13.1	17.4	21.8	42.1	48.1
Eroded Land	Ha	5.28	5.61	6.69	4.46	7.51	10.37	5.03
	%	5.1	5.4	6.5	4.3	7.2	10.0	4.9
Rock Outcrop	Ha	3.83	5.97	3.83	2.11	1.29	5.74	0.84
	%	3.7	5.8	3.7	2.0	1.2	5.5	0.8
Vegetation	Ha	9.89	5.2	1.07	1.55	1.57	4.11	1.94
	%	9.5	4.9	1.0	1.5	1.5	3.9	1.9
Farmland	Ha	64.56	68.92	69.83	70.86	64.67	34.82	24.36
	%	62.2	66.4	67.3	68.3	62.3	33.6	23.5
Bare land	Ha	7.45	5.34	6.85	4.87	4.26	3.22	20.49
	%	7.2	5.2	6.6	4.7	4.2	3.1	19.7
Water body	Ha	1.92	1.91	1.88	1.89	1.87	1.88	1.18
	%	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.1
Total	Ha	103.78	103.78	103.78	103.78	103.78	103.78	103.78
	%	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Authors (2025)

As shown in Table 4, the study revealed that the built-up experienced a steady increase over the observed period from 1993 to 2023 (Figure 2-8). The area coverage of the built-up grew from 10.85 hectares (10.5%) in 1993 to 49.94 hectares (48.1%) in 2023. Similarly, eroded land areas experienced an exponential growth over the observed period. As depicted in Table 4, the eroded land areas grew from 5.28 hectares (5.1%) in 1993 to 6.69 hectares (6.5%) in 2003. After which the gully eroded spatial extent decreased in the year 2008 with 4.46 hectares (4.3%) and then increased to 10.37 hectares (10.0%) in year 2018 representing the highest gully eroded land coverage during the study period.

Vegetation areas experienced a decrease between 1993 and (1998 figure 2-13) from

9.89 hectares (9.5%) to 5.2 hectares (4.9%). It was also found that afterward, there was a decline in the area coverage from 1.57 hectares in 2008 to 1.57 hectares in 2013 with 1.5% each and subsequently increased to 4.11 hectares (3.9%) in 2018.

A fluctuating pattern in farmland was observed during the study period with year 2008 having the highest spatial extent of 70.86 hectares (68.3%). After which there was a continuous decline in the area extent covered by farmland during the study period (Table 6). As showed in Figures 2–8 is the illustration of the Land Use Land Cover classification maps of the study area for the study year. The attributed to the change in rainfall pattern in the study area, (Mbaya *et-al.*, 2022).

Figure 2: Land Use Land Cover Classification Map of Gombe in 1993
Source: Authors (2025)

Figure 3: Land Use Land Cover Classification Map of Gombe in 1998
Source: Authors (2025)

Figure 4: Land Use Land Cover Classification Map of Gombe in 2003
Source: Authors (2025)

Figure 5: Land Use Land Cover Classification Map of Gombe in 2008
Source: Authors (2025)

Figure 6: Land Use Land Cover Classification Map of Gombe in 2013
Source: Authors (2025)

Figure 7: Land Use Land Cover Classification Map of Gombe in 2018
Source: Authors (2025)

Figure 8: Land Use Land Cover Classification Map of Gombe in 2023

Source: Authors (2025)

The percentage cover of bare lands showed an unsteady pattern from 7.45 hectares (7.2%) in the year 1993 to 5.34 hectares (5.2%) and 6.85 hectares (6.6%) in the years 1998 and 2003 respectively. Afterward, observed was a decrease as the percentage land coverage was 4.7% in the year 2008, 4.2% in 2013 and 3.1% in 2018. Afterward, the area coverage for the bare land increased from 3.22 hectares (3.1%) in 2008 to 20.49 hectares (19.7%) in 2023. For water body LULC, a steady percentage land coverage of 1.8% was observed in each of the years during the study period except in the year 2023 where it decreased to 1.1%

representing the least. The decrease in shrubland, water body, and wetland were also linked to rainfall variability and climate change resulting from increasing deforestation, and increasing use of wetland for farming activities, this can be supported by the study of Tatek et al. (2021).

PERIODIC CHANGE IN LAND USE LAND COVER

Table 5 presents the percentage periodic change in land use land cover from 1993 to 2023 in the study area

Table 5: Percentage Periodic Change in Land Use Land Cover

LULC		1993-1998	1998-2003	2003-2008	2008-2013	2013-2018	2018-2023
Built-up	Km ²	0.06	2.72	4.41	4.57	21.03	6.3
	%	0.6	24.9	32.4	25.3	93.0	14.4
Eroded Land	Km ²	0.33	1.08	-2.23	3.05	2.86	-5.34
	%	6.3	19.3	-33.3	68.4	38.1	-51.5
Rock Outcrop	Km ²	2.14	-2.14	-1.72	-0.82	-4.45	-4.90
	%	55.9	-35.8	-44.9	-38.9	-345.0	-85.4
Vegetation	Km ²	-4.77	-4.05	0.48	0.02	2.54	-2.17
	%	-48.2	-79.1	44.9	1.3	161.8	-52.8
Farmland	Km ²	4.36	0.91	1.03	-6.19	-29.85	-10.46
	%	6.8	1.3	1.5	-8.7	-46.2	-30.0
Bare land	Km ²	-2.11	1.51	-1.98	-0.61	-1.04	17.27
	%	-28.3	28.3	-28.9	-2.5	-24.4	536.3
Water body	Km ²	-0.01	-0.03	-0.01	-0.02	-0.01	-0.70
	%	-0.5	-1.8	-0.5	-1.1	-0.5	-37.2

Source: Authors (2025)

The study revealed that there was a steady positive percentage periodic change in the built-up land use land cover type (Table 7). It showed that the highest percentage periodic change was between 2013 and 2018 with 93.0%, followed by 32.4% between 2003 and 2008 (figure 14-15). This implies that there was a steady increase in built-up areas in the study area. The period 1993-1998 (0.6%) indicated the least percentage periodic change in the built-up. Eroded land showed the highest percentage periodic change of 68.4% during 2008-2013, followed by 38.1% during 2013-2018. The least percentage periodic change was observed during 1993-1998 with 6.3%. On the other hand, 2018-2023 and 2003-2008 periods with -51.5% and -33.3% showed a negative percentage periodic change in area covered by eroded land. A similar result was explored.

For rock outcrop, a negative percentage periodic change in area covered was observed in each of the period ranging from -35.8% during 1998-2003 period to -85.4% between 2018 and 2023. The highest negative percentage periodic change was recorded during 2013-2018 with -345.0%. However, a positive percentage periodic change in area extent covered by rock outcrop was recorded during 1993-1998 period with 55.9%. A positive percentage periodic change in the area covered by vegetation was observed during 2013-2018 and 2003-2008 periods only with 161.8% and 49.9% respectively. Vegetation areas experienced a negative percentage periodic change which was highest during 1998-2003 with -79.1%, followed by -52.8% between 2018 and 2023. The findings of this research show that unless proper measure is taken against the LULC changes,

the rate of eroded land is expected to increase as reported Chun Xia Liang *et al.* (2019).

As shown in Table 5, there was a positive percentage periodic change in farmland coverage recorded during the first three (3) periods in the study area with 1993-1998 (6.8%) period having the highest while 1998-2003 (1.3%) period indicated the least. On the other hand, a negative percentage periodic change in area covered by farmland was observed during the last three periods in the study period. This varied from -8.7% during 2008-2013 period to -the highest -46.2% during 2013-2018 period is similar to the findings by Buster Percy *at el.* (2024). The highest positive percentage periodic change of bare land was 536.3% during 2018-2023 period, while was the period 1998-2003 with 28.3% show the least percentage periodic change for bare land. Nevertheless, a negative percentage periodic change was observed between 2003 and 2008 (-28.9%), followed by 1993-1998 (-28.3%) period while 2008-2013 with -2.5% represented the least. Regarding the water body, a negative percentage periodic change in area coverage was recorded in each of the period in the study area ranging from -0.5% to -37.2% during the 2018-2023 period as supported by Akinlabi *et al.* (2021) and Benjamin (2017).

GULLY ERODED LANDSCAPE EXPANSION IN THE STUDY AREA FROM 1993 TO 2023

EXTENT OF GULLY ERODED LANDSCAPE

Table 6 presents the extent of gully eroded land expansion in the study area between 1993 and 2023.

Table 6: Extent of Gully Eroded Land Expansion

		1993	1998	2003	2008	2013	2018	2023
Gully	Extent (km ² .)	5.28	5.61	6.69	4.46	7.51	10.37	5.03
	%	11.7	2.5	14.9	9.9	16.7	23.1	11.2

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

The study revealed that the total area covered by gullies in the study area was 44.95 sq km. Evident was the steady rise in the expansion of gullies in the study area from 5.28 sq km in the year 1993 to 10.37 sq km in the year 2018. Plates I showed various gully sites in the study area. The findings of this study brought out some of the interesting and also significant changes in the land use land cover of Gombe metropolis can have significant impact on the gully in the study area, as the result of changes in the rainfall pattern in the study area can have devastating impact on the gully eroded

land in Gombe metropolis. This supported by the study of Géant Basimine *et al*, (2021) that gullies were increasing not only in number but also in characteristics such as gully length and headcut, Debbie (2024) and Amanawa *et al.*, (2024), investigates the assessment of gully erosion expansion in Ikeduru LGA, Imo State, Nigeria (2017 to 2022). Study thus concludes that our environment is a part of our social and economic survival, and what happens within the environment in which we live can negatively impact our survival.

Plate I: Gully Site at Jauro Kuna in Gombe metropolis

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Although, there was a drop in 2008 as the result of change in rainfall pattern the study area with maximum 314.60mm, but afterward it began to increase again and finally came down to 5.03 sq km in 2023 (Table 6). Increase in annual rainfall particularly in the year 2018 (294.00) from 2017 (1040.90) might be the possible explanation for the increase in the extent of gully expansion in the year 2018. This result depicts that development of gullies has become a perennial environmental menace

that require urgent attention in the study area. Table, 8, showed that the year 2018 recorded the highest extent of gully eroded land expansion during the period with 23.1%, followed by 16.7% in the year 2013. It was found that the least extent of gully expansion was in the year 2008 which accounted for only 9.9%. The findings of this study corroborate those of Nkemakonam and Arinza (2019).

CAUSAL RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LAND USE /LAND COVER CHANGE AND GULLY ERODED LANDSCAPES EXPANSION

LAND USE LAND COVER AND GULLY ERODED LANDSCAPES EXPANSION

The cause and effect or causal relationship between landuse/landcover and gully eroded land in the study area was determined using multiple regression statistics and the results are contained in Table 7.

Tables 7: Relationship between Landuse/Landcover and Gully Eroded Land

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.20 ^a	0.564	0.226	2.34556

a. Predictors: (Constant), water body, Vegetation, Rock outcrop, Built up area, Bareland, Farmland

Source: Author’s data analysis, 2025

Tables 8: Differences between Landuse/Landcover and Gully Eroded Land

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24.593	6	4.099	5.453	0.002
	Residual	.000	0	.		
	Total	24.593	6			

a. Dependent Variable: Gully eroded land

b. Predictors: (Constant), water body, Vegetation, Rock outcrop, Built up area, Bareland, Farmland.

Source: Authors (2025)

Table 9: Impact of Landuse Landcover on Gully Eroded Land

Model	Coefficients							
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Correlations		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Zer order	Partial	Part
(Constant)	13.780	2.11		23.1				
Built up area	1.340	0.4500	-7.933	1.2	0.03	.382	0.300	0.362
Rock outcrop	2.111	22.000	-1.011	2.23	0.04	.425	-0.240	-0.322
Vegetation	1.320	34.000	-1.557	0.34	0.01	-.077	0.510	0.441
Farmland	3.310	2.000	-9.398	2.23	0.01	-.328	0.110	0.430
Bareland	2.234	11.000	-2.919	1.2	0.02	-.442	0.430	0.241
water body	-1.234	18.000	-.133	2.25	0.09	.267	0.330	-0.011

A. Dependent Variable: Gully eroded landscapes

Source: Authors (2025)

Results of the multiple regression statistics shows that landuse landcover variables have statistically significant impact or causal relationship with gully eroded land in Gombe metropolis ($p = 0.002$, $R^2 = 0.564$, $df = 6$, $F = 5.453$, $SE = 2.34556E$). The coefficient of multiple determinations is 0.564 implying that landuse/landcover explained 56.4% of the variation observed in eroded landscape in the study area. The linear relationship between landuse/landcover and gully eroded land in Gombe metropolis is given as:

$$y = 13.78 + 1.340x_1 + 2.11x_2 + 1.320x_3 + 3.310x_4 + 2.234x_5 - 1.234x_6$$

where, y is gullying eroded land, x_1 is built up area, x_2 is rock outcrop, x_3 is vegetation, x_4 is farmland, x_5 is bare land and x_6 is water body.

Table 10, shows the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) conducted to establish the relationship between land use land cover and the gully eroded land expansion in the study area.

Table 10: Correlation between Land Use Land Cover and Gully Eroded Land Expansion

LULC	Built-up	Rock Outcrop	Vegetation	Farm land	Bare land	Water body	Eroded land
Built-up	1						
Rock Outcrop	-.272	1					
Vegetation	-.311	.462	1				
Farm land	-.962**	.158	.089	1			
Bare land	.542	-.536	-.23	-.630	1		
Water body	-.731	.567	.287	.763*	-.958**	1	
Eroded land	.382	.425	-.077	-.328	-.442	.267	1

Source: Authors (2025)

** Correlation is Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

* Correlation is Significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The results in Table 10 show a moderate positive correlation coefficient ($r = 661$) between rock outcrop and gully eroded land. This relationship between the two variables was found not to be statistically significant at both 0.01 and 0.05 significant levels. This portrays that increase in the area covered by rock outcrop tends to increase the of extent gully eroded land in the study area. Similarly, a weak positive relationship was observed to exist between built-up and gully eroded land ($r = .382$) as well as between water body and gully eroded land ($r = .267$). This weak positive relationship was statistically not significant. On the other hand, negative relationships existed between bare land and gully eroded land, and also this negative

relationship was observed between farmland and gully eroded land. This suggests that increase in bare land and farmland will lead to a decrease in gully eroded land and vis-à-vis. As indicated in Table, 14, a strong negative relationship was found to exist between built-up and farmland land use land cover types ($r = -962$). This negative relationship showed to be statistically significant. Also, bare land and water body showed a statistically significant strong negative relationship. This is an indication that an increase in built-up area usually results to decrease in the area covered by farmland.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study assessed the impact of land use land cover on gully eroded land in Gombe metropolis, Gombe state, Nigeria. The study established that land use land cover over time has varied in the study area. Complex interdependent mechanisms between land use land cover classes and soil erodability have reduced infiltration, which caused a higher surface runoff and gully development in the area. It is hereby concluded that gully erosion

development in the study area is on the increase as influenced by changes in the rate of land use land cover, which is causing serious land degradation thereby affecting the people and their economic activities.

Based on the findings of the study, land use land cover of the study area and large-scale water abstraction are the major drivers of land use changes. Therefore, there should be proper water resource management and planning within the study area. Large scale afforestation and biodiversity conservation programs and projects should be established in order to revive the lost vegetation in the study area.

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